

Prevalence of Social Maladjustment Behaviours Among Secondary School Students in Benin Metropolis of Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Social maladjustment behaviours are intentional and conscious failure in responding and adjusting to societal expectations, communication and positive acknowledgements in interpersonal interactions. Within the school environment, it could reduce academic interests, involvement as well as the achievement of academic goals. This study describes social maladjustment among in-school adolescents as the consistent and intentional participation in activities that portrays academic indifferences, disruptive, undisciplined, antisocial and violent behaviours, inadequate interaction, shyness and peer influence. To ascertain its prevalence among in-school adolescents, this study examined the percentage based on parents' socio-economic status, peer influence and sex among the selected school. This study adopted the descriptive survey design on a population of five thousand seven hundred and ninety-four (5794) registered students in mixed public senior secondary schools in Benin Metropolis. The simple random sampling was used to select a sample of three hundred and forty-nine (349) students (162 male and 187 female students). The instrument for data collection titled Social Maladjustment Scale (SMS). The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square test of differences at 0.05 level of significance. The study found the selected participants to be socially maladjusted irrespective of their parents' socioeconomic status, peer influence and sex. It was recommended that in-school adolescents should be educated through psycho education on the negative consequences of socially maladjusted behaviours and therapeutic interventions would be effective in rehabilitating victims and perpetrators.

Keywords: Prevalence, Social Maladjustment Behaviour, Secondary School Student and Benin Metropolis

Introduction

Social maladjustment behaviours among school children that is perceived to be on the increase. This could be owed to disturbing flagrant disobedience to constituted authorities, consistent intentional engagements in unacceptable behaviours among others. According to Animasahun and Aremu (2015), social maladjustment among students are actions or inactions about stipulated school conduct such as regular school attendance and punctuality, completion of homework/assignments, good conduct in tests and exams, appropriate dressing, respect for seniors and teachers, peaceful resolution of conflicts, team spirit and non-violence, among others. In educational and clinical psychology, social maladjustment was defined by Olatunyi (2012) as the persistent and intentional patterns of violating school norms, rules and regulations through behaviours such as multiple acts of truancy, disrespectful and disruptive behaviours, and poor participation in academic activities, substance abuse and sexual abuse among others.

Social maladjustment from the researcher's may be regarded as an intentional and conscious failure in responding and adjusting to interpersonal and societal expectations, communication and positive acknowledgements. Within the school, social maladjustment can be described as the consistent and intentional participation in activities that portrays academic indifferences, disruptive, undisciplined, antisocial and violent behaviours, inadequate interaction, shyness and peer influence. Perpetrators of social maladjusted behaviours could appear normal, knowledgeable and capable of appropriate behaviour as well as conformation to the school and societal norms. These behaviours could be identified by struggles with figures of authority, high frustration threshold, restiveness and manipulative behaviours. Research suggests that social maladjustment behaviours is pervasive across schools, cultures, and countries, with evidence of intentionality. However, when viewed from three major perspectives of education, psychiatric and psychology, Busse and Yim (2013) posited that the educational perspective considers social maladjustment as a conduct or antisocial problem in which maladjusted individuals choose not to conform to socially acceptable rules and norms in the educational environment; the psychiatric perspective as a behaviour indicating failure in the individual's adaptive capacity and also as an adjustment disorder caused by a reaction to psychosocial stressors. Finally, the psychological perspective as a disorder is characterized by antisocial and disruptive behaviour. Notably, some social analysts posited that inadequate social interaction is linked with perpetrators of crimes, violent behaviours and peer rejections (Mutekwe & Mutekwe 2013, Mumthas & Muhsina

2014). Therefore, Social maladjustment as a multidimensional construct whose term covers a wide range of biological, psychological and social conditions where an individual intentionally defy certain rules and regulations or norms.

Within the school environment which is the focus of this present study, socially maladjusted behaviours include academic indifferences, antisocial behaviours, bullying behaviours, disruptive behaviours and undisciplined behaviours manifested in form of maladaptive behaviour in schools. Notable behavioural examples are consistent disobedience to teachers, poor adherence to school rules and regulations, illegal possession of school and other students, appearance in unauthorized and assorted dresses, unlawful punishment of junior students, consumption of alcohol and illicit substances, gangs and secret cult involvements, malpractices of all shades in exams, sexual and unhealthy relationships, leaving class and school without permission, falsehood and fighting (Peralta-Sachez et al. 2009). Partridge (2015) support these claims and also posited that these unacceptable behaviours among adolescent boys and girls are not acceptable and have eroded the moral, educational, psychological and social value expected in our society. Busse and Yim (2013) categorized maladjusted behaviours into internal (intrinsic) and external (extrinsic) driven thoughts. They also stated that the internal or intrinsic maladjusted behaviours are disparities among an individual's desires, propelling and motivating factors and the derived values. The external or extrinsic maladjusted behaviours are failure to meet cultural or societal expectations. Both are intentional behaviours also known as social maladjustment but differ in their motivational drives or energy. Hatter (2023) described social maladjustment as an exclusionary clause from serious emotional disturbances where perpetrators intentionally engage in unacceptable behaviours that cannot be explained by intellectual, sensory or health factors.. Okon (2013) supported this description by stating that social maladjustment is a poor, faulty or inadequate adjustment, a failure to assume the proper, exact or conforming position for adequate function. The researcher's review of these definitions reveals that social maladjusted behaviours are conscious, deliberate, purposeful and intentional failure in adapting to social and environmental demands which may lead to ineffectiveness. Depending on the personal traits and other possible influencing factors, socially maladjusted behaviours could be situation specific and exhibited in on certain occasions. Therefore, social maladjustment is the intentional and conscious engagement in behaviours that instantiates academic indifferences, disruptive, antisocial, undisciplined violent and shyness behaviours which could be influenced by peers.

Ordu and Nnam (2017) qualitatively described social maladjustment behaviours into three categories; which includes the victims, perpetrators and observers. They also stated that this behaviour is capable of influencing the uniqueness of any of these categories earlier mentioned. Similarly, Chirchir, Aruasa, and Chebon (2018) posited that socially maladjusted individuals tend to have a lower commitment to self-development, self-regulation and self-concept. This could lead to reduced tests and examination performances and increased occurrences of truancy. Restrepo et al. (2016) also supported the earlier findings from their study stating that other problems of social maladjustments include withdrawal and uncooperative behaviours. The common characteristics of socially maladjusted adolescents could be reflected in the aspects of life such as family, school, learning environment and social settings. Such characteristics include the inability to adjust to the classroom or handle class tasks effectively, uncoordinated behaviours in the home environment, and the failure in positive association with peers in a non-threatening manner, among others.

The occurrence of social maladjustment among adolescent students from the researcher's review is on the increase and some studies has linked this to suspicious negative social support and insecure attachment (Miller *et al.*, 2015). Suicide attempters are more likely to report inadequate social support networks and lower levels of perceived social support and poor clinical and community controls despite continuous interventions (Hirsch & Bart 2011).

In the cross-sectional survey study by Ordu and Nnam (2017), social maladjustment and family disruption as determinants of criminality among youths was investigated. Among the detained male inmates, the offences of crimes range from involvement in kidnapping, cultism, murder, and armed robbery to burglary among others detained in the Abakaliki prisons, located in Ebonyi State of Nigeria constitute the target population. From the records, simple random sampling was used in the selection of 212 participants. The study revealed a significant relationship between criminality and maladjusted behaviours among male youths. On percentage; 34% and 35.8% of those who committed various offences strongly agreed and agreed respectively that social maladjustment behaviours contributed to their involvement in criminal activities.

In another study, Agoha and Igbokwe (2016) investigated the big five as predictors of social maladjustment among University Undergraduate students. 164 students from a private University who ranged between 19 and 24 years of age were selected as the participants. Out of this, 126 formed 76.80% for females and 38 participants which formed 23.20% were males. Students maladjustment was

measured based on the Big-Five measures of personality. Neuroticism was positively associated with maladjustment, Negative associations were found for Agreeableness and Conscientiousness and Openness. Smith *et al.* (2012), also found that an insecure attachment style, characterized by difficulties trusting others and tolerating closeness and intimacy was associated with suicide-related behaviours among adult psychiatric patients and community members. Among adolescents, insecure attachments and perceived low social supports increases the risk of engaging in maladjustments and possibly suicidal behaviours.

Personality formation process among teenagers was studied by Burtovaya (2020). On one hand was the formation of peculiarities to prevent egocentrism generally and cognitive activity egocentrism and both were studied as properties of personality development. The review emphasized the role of various learning techniques in the development of decantation to reduce egocentrism. There was an interrelation between egocentric personality and cognitive responses which implies that adolescents are influenced by egocentric speech and rigid thinking as well as maladjusted behaviours. The intervention pedagogy, psychologists and health care took into account the education and upbringing as this may not decline with age. Therefore, correction and prevention should form the primary objectives of schools and the psychologist should collaborate with teachers and parents for comprehensive process of social rehabilitation.

In a study on social maladjustment as an indicator effect between childhood sexual abuse, physical abuse, and suicidal behaviour, Stronach *et al.* (2011) found that people with a history of sexual or physical abuse in childhood often have difficulty forming and maintaining social relationships with others and are more likely to develop and maintain avoidant and anxious attachment styles in adulthood than those who have not been abused. However, few studies, to the investigator's knowledge, have investigated social maladjustment as a third variable explaining or changing the relationship between child maltreatment and suicidal behaviour. Smith *et al.* (2012) also explored the role of social maladjustment in the relationship between childhood abuse and suicidal behaviour and found that social maladjustment was associated with increased ideation of death in a sample of women who had experienced childhood sexual abuse and depression.

In a study, Dario (2012) investigated the effect of social maladjustment at age 11 on the probability of adult employment. Social maladjustment was measured according to the British Social Adjustment

Guide score provided by the National Study of Child Development. This provides information on cohort members in both childhood and adulthood, including employment status. Current and previous employment history, the econometric method consisting of a dynamic probit model and unobserved heterogeneity was used to explain the problems of dependence on the real state and initial conditions. In agreement with previous works in the literature, it was found that social maladjustment during childhood predicts a lower probability of employment in adulthood. This result also holds for controlling the state dependency and past work history. Interestingly, socially maladjusted children's probability of adult employment is prone to greater variability across life experiences than socially adjusted children. Earlier employment, education, young adult work experiences, and early work experiences, especially for women, were found to increase the likelihood of adult employment for all members of the cohort. However, the positive effect is stronger for socially maladjusted children and, in general, investment in higher education appears to be relevant. This suggests that interventions in the developmental stage of socially maladjusted children could be important in reducing inequality in the employment probability of adults.

Carey and Richards (2014) in a longitudinal study explored the reciprocal and perpetuating relationship between exposure to violence and childhood social maladjustment among urban African American youth. Participants in this study were 268 African American students (age $M = 11.65$ years, 40% male and 60% female) from six downtown Chicago public schools in high-crime neighbourhoods. The data used was collected over three years on measures of demographic information, exposure to community violence, and social adjustment. Hypotheses were tested using structural equation modelling (SEM) and results revealed that exposure to community violence was not consistently linked to social maladjustment. The transactional results also revealed that there are certain periods in development when increased social maladjustment may put youth at risk of increased exposure to violence. From the results presented, this study has important implications for interventions for inner-city youth exposed to violence.

Statement of the Problem

The academic and behavioural adjustment of students could be affected by poor development, and influence from peers among others. Group association appears to exert influence on adolescents who belong to and participate in these activities. The socially maladjusted adolescent can be rebellious against their parents, staying out late or even absconding from home. At school, such could be seen as

violating school rules and regulations, confronting disciplinary measures fighting and unwarranted disruptions in class, rude and unmannered responses to teachers and school authorities, mimicking and cajoling or violent insightful behaviours. These unacceptable behaviours exhibited by socially maladjusted students could result from poor self-control, temper tantrums, use of foul language, pilfering or vandalism, and truancy (Mandelli et al. 2011). These inappropriate behaviours are often not accepted by their colleagues and peers.

Careful observation from the researcher's perspective as a counsellor and an educator revealed that socially maladjusted behaviours are increasing among public school students, despite their knowledge and abilities to conform to known expectations. This is evident from frequent disobedience to teachers and students in authority positions, bullying, disruptive behaviours, use of abusive words, coming late to school, failure to do or submit homework, and appearance in unrecognized school uniforms, to mention but a few. These behaviours are majorly exhibited in the school environment, some parents often claim that the source of their child's behaviour originated from the school, thereby blaming the teachers and school authorities. Meanwhile, school staff also become frustrated with what is perceived as weak parenting and decadence in society. The researcher is concerned about the nation's education and leadership development. The problem of this study is to examine the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour among students and ascertain whether peer influence, gender, and parent's socio-economic status can influence the respondents' views of the above stated problem.

Objectives of the Study

This study explored the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviours among senior secondary students in public schools in the Benin Metropolis of Edo State. Specifically, it assessed the influence of socioeconomic status, peer influence, and sex on this prevalence.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on the Behavioural Decision Theory (BDT) propounded by Herbert Simon in 1947. Decision-making theory first appeared in his renowned book *Administrative Behaviour* in 1947 which suggested that decisions are critical because if they are not made in time they will negatively impact the goals. The frameworks to explain the phenomenon of decision-making are often divided into two types: normative and descriptive theory. The former aims to support rational decision-making, while the latter describes how people make decisions. This theory challenged the classical rational

choice theory, proposing that individuals make decisions based on bounded rationality. This theory suggests that cognitive limitations, emotional factors, and environmental constraints influence decision-making processes. Simon argued that humans simplify complex decisions by using mental shortcuts, rules of thumb, and satisficing strategies, leading to suboptimal choices.

Adolescents, particularly those in school, exhibit bounded rationality when facing decisions. Social pressures, emotional impulsivity, and cognitive immaturity contribute to suboptimal choices. In-school adolescents often prioritize short-term gains over long-term consequences, leading to social maladjustment behaviours like aggression, substance abuse, or delinquency. These behaviours stem from impulsive decisions, driven by emotional reactivity rather than rational consideration.

The Behavioural Decision Theory helps explain the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviours among in-school adolescents. Factors like peer influence, emotional dysregulation, and lack of future orientation contribute to poor decision-making. Adolescents may engage in risky behaviours to cope with distress or seek social validation for their actions. Simon's theory highlights the importance of understanding cognitive and social limitations in adolescent decision-making, informing interventions targeting social maladjustment behaviours.

Research Questions

1. What is the prevalence level of social maladjustment behaviour among secondary school students in Benin Metropolis, Nigeria?
2. What are the differences in the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour based on parents' socioeconomic status?
3. What are the differences in the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour based on peer influence?
4. What are the differences in the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour based on sex?

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of this study was five thousand seven hundred and ninety-four (5794) registered students in mixed public senior secondary schools in Benin Metropolis. The simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of three hundred and forty-nine (349) senior secondary class two (2) students (162 male and 187 female students). The instrument used for this study was titled "Social Maladjustment Scale (SMS). The instrument was adapted from three different sources, that is; Ibadin and Akpede (2021), Peralta-Sachez, et al., (2009), and Wiggins (1969)". The instrument has two (2) sections, (A and B). Section A has nine (9) items on

demographic information and parents' socioeconomic status while section B has forty (40) items from seven (7) sub-categories to measure social maladjustment. These sub-categories include academic indifferences; aggressive behaviour against peers (bullying); aggression against teachers and undisciplined behaviours; disruptive indiscipline; antisocial and violent behaviour; inadequate interactions; shyness and peer influence. The respondents indicated the extent of social maladjustment on five-point scale from 'always: 5 points, often: 4 points, rarely: 3 points, occasionally: 2 points and never: 1 point. The instrument was validated by two (2) psychometric experts in the department of Educational Evaluation and Counselling Psychology. Their corrections, suggestions and amendments were implemented in the instrument used. The instrument had a coefficient vale of 0.93 using Cronbach's Alpha statistics. The data collected were analysed using Chi-square test of differences, Descriptive Statistics and Regression statistics was used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of the data analysis is presented below as follows;

Research Question 1: What is the prevalence level of social maladjustment behaviour among secondary school students in Benin Metropolis, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive on the Prevalence of Social Maladjustment Behaviours among Senior Secondary School Class Two (2) Students in Benin Metropolis.

S/N	Statement	N	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.
1	I refuse to do classwork, assignments or homework.	349	2.76	1.45
2	I make respectful remarks to teachers.	349	4.21	1.29
3	I make annoying remarks about assignments.	349	2.16	1.37
4	I like to skip classes.	349	1.38	.93
5	I and my classmates throw things in class.	349	1.79	1.25
6	I and my friends allow others participate in some group activities.	349	3.11	1.68
7	Acting rudely towards other classmates makes me superior.	349	1.42	1.05
8	I leave the class when teaching is going on.	349	1.35	.95
9	I talk back at teachers to intimidate them.	349	1.29	.81
10	I belong to gangs that fight teachers in school.	349	1.13	.65
11	Insulting and embarrassing teachers makes me bigger than others.	349	1.15	.64
12	Gossiping about teachers excites me.	349	1.60	1.14
13	I interrupt and distract others in class during teaching	349	1.44	.93
14	I arrive late or wait around with friends before coming into the classroom	349	1.64	1.12

15	I dislike following class rules	349	1.53	1.16
16	I talk and distract others while the teacher is talking	349	1.35	.97
17	I take drugs and alcohol in school.	349	1.13	.66
18	I play pranks on teachers to have fun.	349	1.37	1.02
19	I have been in trouble with the police.	349	1.07	.48
20	I wrecked my teacher's belongings.	349	1.27	.87
21	I prefer to pass by friends and people I know I have not seen for a long time unless they speak to me first.	349	2.63	1.56
22	I cannot mix and make new friends easily.	349	3.27	1.56
23	I do not like being made fun of	349	2.69	1.64
24	I like to party and have other affairs where there is lot of loud fun	349	2.09	1.43
25	I put on the stunt in the class and school to set a record.	349	1.72	1.25
26	I like to frequently show others that I am bashful	349	1.71	1.26
27	I find it hard to talk when I meet new people	349	3.28	1.87
28	I wish I were not so shy	349	3.32	1.61
29	When in a school, I have trouble thinking of the right thing to talk about	349	2.61	1.65
30	I cannot speak to people in school and in my class until they speak to me first	349	2.26	1.43
31	In school, I find it very hard to talk before the class	349	2.77	1.66
32	I cannot make friends as quickly as others do	349	2.98	1.65
33	I find it hard to stick-up for my right because am so reserved	349	2.57	1.53
34	I frequently ask people for advice	349	3.29	1.56
35	My friends and I think that some school rules should not be obeyed.	349	1.74	1.26
36	My friends and I believe that nothing is illegal.	349	1.38	.91
37	My friends and I fight others to show we are in-charge.	349	1.25	.82
38	Some of my friends taught me how to disobey law and order.	349	1.32	.92
39	I and my friends enjoy talking about how we fought and destroyed things.	349	1.37	1.01
40	My friend's fight is mine, and mine is theirs.	349	2.41	1.70
Average		349	3.94	2.37

The descriptive analysis in the table 1 provides an insight into the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviours among secondary school adolescents. The average Mean (\bar{x}) = 3.94 indicates a moderate level of social maladjustment behaviours. While the moderate Standard Deviation (SD) = 2.37 suggests variability, but relatively consistent experiences.

Research Question 2: What are the differences in the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour based on parents' socioeconomic status?

Table 2: Chi-Square test of difference in prevalence of Socially Maladjustment adolescents by PSES

		Sociallymal		Total
		Not Maladjusted	Maladjusted	
Low	within PSES	94.0	6.0	100.0
	within Sociallymal	46.6	71.4	47.6
Moderate	within PSES	97.7	2.3	100.0
	within Sociallymal	51.6	28.6	50.7
High	within PSES	100.0		100.0
	within Sociallymal	1.8%		1.7
Total	within PSES	96.0	4.0	100.0
	within Sociallymal	100.0	100.0	100.0

$\chi^2 = 3.407$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $df = 2$, $p\text{-value} = .182$; **No Difference**

Results in Table 2 show a Chi-Square test of difference in the prevalence of students who are socially maladjusted in the selected secondary schools based on parents' socioeconomic status. The $\chi^2 = 3.407$, with a degree of freedom = 2, and a p-value = .182. Testing at 0.05 alpha (α) level, the p-value is greater than alpha level. Hence; there is no difference in the prevalence of students who are socially maladjusted in the selected secondary schools' class two (2) based on parents' socioeconomic status.

Research Question 3: What are the differences in the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour based on peer influence?

Table 3: Chi-Square test of difference in prevalence of Socially Maladjustment adolescents by Peer Influence

		Sociallymal		Total
		Not Maladjusted	Maladjusted	
Low	within Peerinfluence	97.3	2.7	100.0
	within Sociallymal	98.5	64.3	97.1
High	within Peerinfluence	50.0	50.0	100.0
	within Sociallymal	1.5	35.7	2.9
Total	within Peerinfluence	96.0	4.0	100.0
	within Sociallymal	100.0	100.0	100.0

$\chi^2 = 56.55$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $df = 1$, $p\text{-value} = .000$; there **is a difference**

Results in Table 3 show a Chi-Square test of differences in the prevalence of socially maladjusted students in the selected secondary schools based on peer influence. The $\chi^2 = 56.55$, with a degree of freedom = 1, and a p-value = .000. Testing at 0.05 alpha (α) level, the p-value is Less than the alpha level. Therefore, there is a difference in the prevalence of socially maladjusted students in the selected secondary schools considering their level of peer influence.

Research Question 4: What are the differences in the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviour based on sex?

Table 3: Chi-Square test of difference in prevalence of Socially Maladjustment by Sex

		Sociallymal		Total	
		Not Maladjusted	Maladjusted		
Sex	Male	within sex	95.1	4.9	100.0
		within Sociallymal	46.0	57.1	46.4
	Female	within sex	96.8	3.2	100.0
		within Sociallymal	54.0	42.9	53.6
Total		within sex	96.0	4.0	100.0
		within Sociallymal	100.0	100.0	100.0

$\chi^2 = .674$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $df = 1$, p-value = .411; **No Difference**

Results in Table 3 show a Chi-Square test of difference in the prevalence of students who are socially maladjusted in the selected secondary schools by sex. The $\chi^2 = .674$ with a degree of freedom = 1, and a p-value = .411. Testing at 0.05 alpha (α) level, the p-value is greater than the alpha level. Hence; Therefore, there is no difference in the prevalence of socially maladjusted students in the selected secondary schools considering their level of sex.

Discussion of Findings

The findings for research question one which examined the prevalence of social maladjustment behaviours indicated moderate prevalence. This indicates that social maladjustment behaviours are present, but not severe. This could be owed to the modelling of behaviours among in-school adolescents as some of these behaviours are only exhibited within the school Furthermore, the secondary class two (2) adolescents share similar levels of social maladjustment behaviours. The finding agrees with Doley (2018), who found that adjustment definitely influences the achievements a student. This also agrees

with Bama, (2019,); Oliha and Audu, (2015), who found that personal-emotions, social relations, environmental and academic factors have a significant effect on adjustment among school students.

The data analysis for research question two revealed that there is no difference in the prevalence of socially maladjusted behaviours among students in the selected secondary schools based on parents' socioeconomic status, this is in agreement with the findings of Audu, & Oaikhena (2018), Arogundade and Amure (2015) and Si et al. (2020) who examined and found no relationship between adolescent's rate of maladjustment and parent socio-economic status. However, this result could be due the school ownership because the respondents dominated the moderate parents' socio-economic status.

The result from research question three revealed that there is a difference in the prevalence socially maladjusted behaviours among students in the selected secondary schools considering their level on peer influence. This is in agreement with Akpunne (2018), Moldes et al. (2019), Nwikpo, et al. (2020), who found that a positive correlation exists between social manipulation, multidimensional peer influence and rate of unacceptable behaviours among adolescent students.

The findings of the study in research question four revealed that there is no difference the in prevalence of socially maladjusted behaviours among students in the selected secondary schools considering sex. This finding is in agreement with Olatunyi (2012), Reidy et al. (2018) and Adeoye et al. (2021). They found that the percentage of unacceptable behaviours was equal among adolescent student irrespective of their gender. Although this could be as a result of both sexes being in the same class as such, one sex could imitate the behaviour of the opposite sex.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, social maladjustment behaviours is prevalent at a moderate level among in-school adolescents. However, there was no differences in the prevalence based on parents' socioeconomic status and sex, but based on peer influence, the in-school adolescents were socially maladjusted.

Recommendation

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study;

1. Counsellors and psychologists should be encouraged to embrace therapeutic interventions that have been proven to be effective in the management of social maladjustment behaviours such

- as Social Skills Training, Cognitive Analytic Therapy, Conflict Resolution Therapy among others.
2. Early referral by classroom teachers, parents and school authorities of socially maladjusted students to the counselling professionals is vital for proper management.
 3. Schools counsellors should screen students for signs and symptoms of social maladjustment.
 4. An effective and functional unit for counselling should be established in all secondary schools in Edo state.
 5. Counselling services should be available to all schools levels as recognized by the National Policy on Education.

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